

**PRODUCT OF A NUMBER AND ITS MULTIPLICATIVE
INVERSE, MOMENTS OF L -FUNCTIONS AND EXPONENTIAL
SUMS**

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Received: 3/21/15, Revised: 9/15/15, Accepted: 1/4/16, Published: 1/21/16

Abstract

In this paper, we study the average size of the product of a number and its multiplicative inverse modulo a prime p . This turns out to be related to moments of L -functions and leads to a curious asymptotic formula for a certain triple exponential sum.

1. Introduction and Main Results

Let p be a prime number. For any a such that $(a, p) = 1$, let \bar{a} be the positive integer less than p such that $a\bar{a} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Of course $a\bar{a}$ can be as small as 1 and as large as $(p-1)^2$. So one may ask how large $a\bar{a}$ is on average. This leads us to study

$$S := \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a\bar{a} = \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab. \quad (1)$$

More generally, we define

$$S(d) := \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ ab \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab. \quad (2)$$

We have

Theorem 1. For $(d, p) = 1$,

$$S(d) = \frac{p^3}{4} + O(p^{5/2} \log^2 p).$$

For a Dirichlet character $\chi \pmod{p}$, let $L(s, \chi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\chi(n)}{n^s}$ be the corresponding Dirichlet L -function which has meromorphic continuation over the entire complex plane. As a by-product of our proof of Theorem 1, we have

Corollary 1. For $(d, p) = 1$,

$$\sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d)L(0, \chi)^2 \ll p^{3/2} \log^2 p.$$

One may ask if the error term in Theorem 1 is best possible. For this, we have the following result.

Theorem 2. For any prime p ,

$$\sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \left| S(d) - \frac{p^2(p-1)}{4} \right|^2 = \frac{5}{144} \frac{p^2(p^2-1)^3}{(p^2+1)} + O(p^5 e^{3 \log p / \log \log p}).$$

This tells us that, for some $1 \leq d \leq p-1$, we have

$$\left| S(d) - \frac{p^2(p-1)}{4} \right| \gg p^{5/2}.$$

So the error term in Theorem 1 is sharp apart from the logarithmic factor.

One can also consider a higher dimensional analogue of (2) by defining

$$S_k(d) := \sum_{\substack{a_1=1 \\ a_1 a_2 \dots a_k \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{a_2=1 \\ a_2 \dots a_k \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \dots \sum_{\substack{a_k=1 \\ a_k \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} a_1 a_2 \dots a_k$$

and prove

Theorem 3. For $k \geq 3$ and $(d, p) = 1$,

$$S_k(d) = \frac{p^k(p-1)^{k-1}}{2^k} + O_k(p^{3k/2}(\log p)^k).$$

Here O_k means that the implicit constant may depend on k .

When $k = 3$, one can do slightly better by an exponential sum method and obtain

Theorem 4. For $(d, p) = 1$,

$$S_3(d) = \frac{p^5}{8} + O(p^{9/2}(\log p)^2).$$

The improvement on the error term may not be significant. However, as a by-product of its proof, we derive an interesting weighted triple exponential sum result, namely

Theorem 5. For $(l, p) = 1$,

$$\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} abc e\left(\frac{abc}{p}\right) = -\frac{p^5}{8} + O(p^{9/2} \log^3 p)$$

where $e(x) := e^{2\pi i x}$.

We will leave the interested readers to come up with similar exponential sum results in more variables.

2. Some Lemmas

Lemma 1. For $z \neq 1$ and $z^p = 1$, we have $\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} bz^b = \frac{-p}{1-z}$.

Proof. As $1 + z + z^2 + \dots + z^{p-1} = 0$, one can check directly that

$$\left(\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} bz^b\right)(1-z) = z + z^2 + \dots + z^{p-1} - (p-1)z^p = -1 - (p-1) = -p$$

which gives the lemma after dividing by $1-z$. □

Lemma 2. For $z \neq 1$ and $z^p = 1$, we have $\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-z^b} = \frac{p-1}{2}$.

Proof. Notice that $\frac{1}{1-z} + \frac{1}{1-\bar{z}} = \frac{1-\bar{z}+1-z}{(1-z)(1-\bar{z})} = \frac{1-\bar{z}-z+z\bar{z}}{(1-z)(1-\bar{z})} = 1$ as $|z| = 1$. Therefore

$$\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-z^b} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \left(\frac{1}{1-z^b} + \frac{1}{1-z^{p-b}}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} 1 = \frac{p-1}{2}.$$

□

Lemma 3. For $z \neq 1$, $z^p = 1$ and $1 \leq d < p$, we have $\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{z^{-db}}{1-z^b} = \frac{p-1}{2} - d$.

Proof. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{1-z^{-db}}{1-z^b} &= \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{-z^{-db}(1-z^{db})}{1-z^b} = -\sum_{b=1}^{p-1} z^{-db} \sum_{j=0}^{d-1} z^{jb} \\ &= -\sum_{j=0}^{d-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} z^{(j-d)b} = -\sum_{j=0}^{d-1} (-1) = d. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore by Lemma 2,

$$d = \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-z^b} - \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{z^{-db}}{1-z^b} = \frac{p-1}{2} - \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \frac{z^{-db}}{1-z^b},$$

which gives the lemma after rearranging terms. □

Lemma 4. For any prime p and $(k, p) = 1$,

$$\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{k\bar{a}}{p}\right) \ll p^{3/2} \log p.$$

Proof. By Weil’s bound on incomplete Kloosterman sums (see [1] for example), we have

$$F(u) := \sum_{a=1}^u e\left(\frac{k\bar{a}}{p}\right) \ll p^{1/2} \log p$$

for $1 \leq u < p$. Using this and partial summation,

$$\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{k\bar{a}}{p}\right) = \int_{1^-}^{p-1} u dF(u) = (p-1)F(p-1) - \int_{1^-}^{p-1} F(u) du \ll p^{3/2} \log p.$$

□

Lemma 5. For any integer $p > 1$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} \ll p \log p.$$

Proof. Observe that $|1 - e(-k/p)| \geq |\operatorname{Im}(1 - e(-k/p))| = |\sin 2k\pi/p|$. For $0 \leq k < p/4$, we have $|\sin 2k\pi/p| \geq k/p$ by observing that the sine function is above the line $y = 2x/\pi$ for $0 \leq x \leq \pi/2$. So

$$\sum_{k < p/4} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} \leq \sum_{k < p/4} \frac{1}{k/p} \ll p \log p.$$

Using $\sin(\pi - x) = \sin x$, we have

$$\sum_{p/4 < k \leq p/2} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} \ll p \log p.$$

Hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p/2} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} \ll p \log p + 1 \ll p \log p, \tag{3}$$

where the 1 may come from the term when $k = p/4$. By complex conjugation,

$$\frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} = \frac{1}{|1 - e(-(p-k)/p)|}.$$

So from (3),

$$\sum_{k=p/2}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|} \ll p \log p \tag{4}$$

and the lemma follows from (3) and (4). □

3. Proofs of Theorems 1 and 3 and Corollary 1

Proof of Theorem 1. We use exponential sums to study (2). By the orthogonality of additive characters (see Equation (4.1) in [2], for example),

$$S(d) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab \sum_{k=1}^p e\left(\frac{k(d\bar{a} - b)}{p}\right) = \frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} + \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{k d \bar{a}}{p}\right) \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} be\left(\frac{-kb}{p}\right)$$

where $e(u) := e^{2\pi i u}$. Hence, by Lemma 1,

$$S(d) = \frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{k d \bar{a}}{p}\right). \tag{5}$$

By Lemmas 4 and 5,

$$S(d) = \frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} + O\left(p^{3/2} \log p \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e(-k/p)|}\right) = \frac{p^3}{4} + O(p^{5/2} \log^2 p). \tag{6}$$

□

Another way to study (2) is through character sums.

Proof of Corollary 1. By the orthogonality of Dirichlet characters (see [2], Chapter 4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} S(d) &= \frac{1}{\phi(p)} \sum_{\chi \pmod{p}} \bar{\chi}(d) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab \chi(a) \chi(b) \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab + \frac{1}{\phi(p)} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab \chi(a) \chi(b) \\ &= \frac{p^2(p-1)}{4} + \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) \left(\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \chi(a) \right)^2. \end{aligned}$$

As $\sum_{a \pmod{p}} a \chi(a) = -pL(0, \chi)$ (see [2], page 310) and combine with the functional equation for Dirichlet L -functions), we have

$$S(d) = \frac{p^2(p-1)}{4} + \frac{p^2}{p-1} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) L(0, \chi)^2. \tag{7}$$

Comparing (7) and (6), we deduce

$$\sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) L(0, \chi)^2 \ll p^{3/2} \log^2 p.$$

□

The character sum method can be used to study a higher dimensional analogue of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 3. By the orthogonality of Dirichlet characters (see [2], Chapter 4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_k(d) &= \frac{1}{\phi(p)} \sum_{\chi \pmod{p}} \bar{\chi}(d) \sum_{a_1=1}^{p-1} \sum_{a_2=1}^{p-1} \dots \sum_{a_k=1}^{p-1} a_1 a_2 \dots a_k \chi(a_1) \chi(a_2) \dots \chi(a_k) \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{a_1=1}^{p-1} \sum_{a_2=1}^{p-1} \dots \sum_{a_k=1}^{p-1} a_1 a_2 \dots a_k \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\phi(p)} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) \sum_{a_1=1}^{p-1} \sum_{a_2=1}^{p-1} \dots \sum_{a_k=1}^{p-1} a_1 a_2 \dots a_k \chi(a_1) \chi(a_2) \dots \chi(a_k) \\ &= \frac{p^k (p-1)^{k-1}}{2^k} + \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) \left(\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \chi(a) \right)^k. \end{aligned}$$

As $\sum_{a \pmod{p}} a \chi(a) \ll p^{3/2} \log p$ by the Polya-Vinogradov inequality (see Theorem 9.18 in [2] for example) and partial summation, we have

$$S_k(d) = \frac{p^k (p-1)^{k-1}}{2^k} + O_k(p^{3k/2} (\log p)^k)$$

which gives Theorem 3. □

4. Proof of Theorem 2

Proof of Theorem 2. Define

$$M := \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \left| S(d) - \frac{p^2 (p-1)}{4} \right|^2.$$

By (7),

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \left| \frac{p^2}{p-1} \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \bar{\chi}(d) L(0, \chi)^2 \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{p^4}{(p-1)^2} \sum_{\chi_1 \neq \chi_0} \sum_{\chi_2 \neq \chi_0} L(0, \chi_1)^2 \overline{L(0, \chi_2)^2} \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \bar{\chi}_1(d) \chi_2(d) \\ &= \frac{p^4}{(p-1)} \sum_{\chi_1 \neq \chi_0} |L(0, \chi_1)|^4 = \frac{p^4}{(p-1)} \sum_{\substack{\chi_1 \pmod{p} \\ \chi_1(-1) = -1}} |L(0, \chi_1)|^4 \end{aligned}$$

by the orthogonality of Dirichlet characters (see [2], Chapter 4) and the fact that $L(0, \chi) = 0$ when $\chi(-1) = 1$ (see [2], Chapter 10). As $L(0, \chi) = \frac{\tau(\chi)}{\pi} L(1, \chi)$ and $|\tau(\chi)| = p^{1/2}$ where $\tau(\chi) = \sum_{a=1}^p \chi(a)e(a/p)$ is the Gauss sum,

$$M = \frac{p^6}{\pi^4(p-1)} \sum_{\substack{\chi_1 \pmod{p} \\ \chi_1(-1)=-1}} |L(1, \chi_1)|^4 = \frac{5}{144} \frac{p^2(p^2-1)^3}{(p^2+1)} + O(p^5 e^{3 \log p / \log \log p})$$

by Lemma 2 of Zhang [3]. This tells us that for some $1 \leq d \leq p-1$, we have

$$\left| S(d) - \frac{p^2(p-1)}{4} \right| \gg p^{5/2}.$$

So the error term in (6) is optimal apart from the logarithmic factor. □

5. Double Exponential Sum

In this section, we want to study

$$D := \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab e\left(\frac{lab}{p}\right). \tag{8}$$

First, observe that

$$D = \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{ld}{p}\right) \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ ab \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab.$$

By (5),

$$D = -\frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} - \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{ld}{p}\right) \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{k d \bar{a}}{p}\right).$$

Now the above sum can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{d(l+k\bar{a})}{p}\right) \\ &= -\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \sum_{d=1}^p e\left(\frac{d(l+k\bar{a})}{p}\right) \\ & \quad - \frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} + p \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \frac{a}{1-e(al/p)} \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 2. Therefore

$$D = -p \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \frac{a}{1-e(al/p)}. \tag{9}$$

6. Triple Exponential Xum: proof of Theorem 5

Proof of Theorem 5. In this section, we consider

$$T := \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} abc e\left(\frac{labc}{p}\right)$$

where $0 < l < p$. One can rearrange it as

$$T = \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} c \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} ab e\left(\frac{lcab}{p}\right) = -p \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} c \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \frac{a}{1 - e(ac/p)}$$

by (9). Grouping the sums according to $ac \equiv d \pmod{p}$, we have

$$T = -p \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(dl/p)} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ ac \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} ac.$$

By (5) and Lemma 2,

$$\begin{aligned} T &= -p \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(dl/p)} \left[\frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kda}{p}\right) \right] \\ &= -\frac{p^2(p-1)^3}{8} + p \sum_{d=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(dl/p)} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1 - e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kda}{p}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Theorem 5 follows immediately by observing that (10) has a main term $-p^5/8$ and an error term $O(p^{9/2} \log^3 p)$ using Lemmas 4 and 5. \square

7. Proof of Theorem 4

Proof of Theorem 4. By definition, we have $S_3(d) = \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ abc \equiv d \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} abc$. By the or-

thogonality of additive characters,

$$\begin{aligned} S_3(d) &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} abc \sum_{l=1}^p e\left(\frac{l(abc-d)}{p}\right) \\ &= \frac{p^2(p-1)^3}{8} + \frac{1}{p} \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} e\left(-\frac{dl}{p}\right) \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} abce\left(\frac{labc}{p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

By (10) and Lemma 3,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_3(d) &= \frac{p^2(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} e\left(-\frac{dt}{p}\right) \left[-\frac{p(p-1)^3}{8} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(tl/p)} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kt\bar{a}}{p}\right) \right] \\
 &= \frac{p(p+1)(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \frac{e(-ltd/p)}{1-e(tl/p)} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kt\bar{a}}{p}\right) \\
 &= \frac{p(p+1)(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} \left(\frac{p-1}{2} - t\bar{d}\right) \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kt\bar{a}}{p}\right) =: S_1 + S_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_2 &= \frac{p-1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{kt\bar{a}}{p}\right) + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} t\bar{d} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kt\bar{a}}{p}\right) \\
 &= -\frac{p-1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} t \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{kd\bar{t}\bar{a}}{p}\right) \\
 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{t=1}^{p-1} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ate\left(\frac{kd\bar{t}\bar{a}}{p}\right) \\
 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{kd\bar{c}}{p}\right) \sum_{\substack{t=1 \\ at \equiv c \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} at.
 \end{aligned}$$

By (5),

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_2 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{8} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{kd\bar{c}}{p}\right) \left[\frac{p(p-1)^2}{4} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-l/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{lc\bar{a}}{p}\right) \right] \\
 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{4} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{kd\bar{c}}{p}\right) \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-l/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} ae\left(\frac{lc\bar{a}}{p}\right) \\
 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{4} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-l/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} a \sum_{c=1}^{p-1} e\left(\frac{lc\bar{a} + kd\bar{c}}{p}\right) \\
 &= -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{4} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-k/p)} \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-e(-l/p)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} aS(l\bar{a}, kd; p),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $S(a, b; p)$ is the Kloosterman sum. Using Weil's bound on Kloosterman sums [1] and Lemma 5, we have

$$S_2 = -\frac{p(p-1)^3}{4} + O(p^{9/2} \log^2 p).$$

Consequently,

$$S_3(d) = \frac{p(p-1)^4}{8} + O(p^{9/2} \log^2 p),$$

which gives Theorem 4. \square

Acknowledgments The author would like to thank the anonymous referee's suggestions which greatly improved the exposition of the paper.

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